
SOLAR PANELS AND THEIR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

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Abstract. The problem of rational use of electricity in the current period is discussed in the article. In particular, the issues of observance of energy saving and efficiency in designing residential and industrial buildings are studied. The problems of rational ways to save electricity are also considered in the article in relation to solar panels and the types of their elements. A conclusion is drawn about the types of solar cells and their effective use.

Keywords: solar panels, solar power plants, network power plants, battery, inverter, controller.

In recent years, scientists around the world have been racking their brains to develop competitive, accessible, and inexpensive ways to generate electricity. Some progress is being made in this direction. One such convenient and inexpensive way to generate electricity today is the use of solar panels.

The use of competitive energy sources, including the ones generating electricity using solar panels, is becoming increasingly popular in Uzbekistan. Our country has sunny days for almost twelve months a year, so, there are incredibly optimal conditions for the effective use of solar panels.

At present, a number of remote settlements and social facilities in our country, which have no electricity supply, are provided with energy from solar panels. “Solar lights” are already used in many houses.

Generating electricity from sunlight is recognized as one of the most promising areas. This “blessing of nature” will provide free electricity to millions and millions of people. The most important thing is that its use does not harm the ecology of the environment, does not deplete natural resources, and does not waste labor.

Today, there are more than a dozen companies engaged in the production and sale of solar energy equipment in Uzbekistan. Through them, a consumer can

purchase solar panels and batteries, solar energy collectors, solar electrical systems, solar photovoltaic models, solar water heaters, and solar engineering equipment. Anyone who wishes it can install solar power equipment in their home, yard, or backyard.

The activities in this direction should begin by contacting companies involved in the production or sale of solar energy equipment. Then the specialists come to the apartment and study in detail the buyer’s electricity needs. After that, they suggest purchasing solar panels and batteries that can provide the required amount of electricity.

Solar cells are a fiber-electric converter that converts solar energy directly into electrical current, that is, it presents a semiconductor device placed in special frames and forms solar panels. These frames are used to convert sunlight into electrical current.

Solar panels are called solar power plants. They have 2 different options:

1. Battery-powered panels (autonomous solar power plant, hereinafter referred to as ES)

It is appropriate to install battery-powered ES in places where electricity is not available or there are frequent outages. The panels store the energy they accumulate from the sun in reserve and use it at any time of the day. The pattern of use of the system is: in the event of a sudden power outage, the backup energy of the battery is automatically connected to the network and reaches certain hours.

Its usage system: in the event of a sudden power outage that you are using, the battery backup energy is automatically connected to the network and reaches certain hours.

2. Network power plant. It contains only solar panels and equipment. This plant operates in parallel with the electrical supply network. This method is mainly used for the purpose of saving energy.

The principle of its operation is: that the energy from solar panels can be converted by equipment into a current of 220 or 380 volts and delivered directly to the consumer at night. Excess energy can be used, if necessary, by transferring it to the State Electricity Network.

The cost of solar panels increases depending on their power. For example, a 1.5 or 2 kW panel can provide uninterrupted energy for lighting a home, and connecting a TV, and a computer. The cost of such battery is 6.5-7 million soums rubles. If you want to use a refrigerator and air conditioner, you may have to purchase a 3-4 kW panel. Its cost on average is about 8-10 million soums.

The main purpose of installing solar panels is not to use household appliances, which consume a lot of electricity, but to satisfy the most pressing needs, that is, to

provide the apartment with light. Therefore, it is in many ways beneficial to install such batteries mainly in populated areas where electricity is not available.

Solar energy is mainly generated by 4 devices: solar panel, controller, battery and inverter. They are connected to each other by cables.

The panel thickness is from 30 mm to 5 cm. It is adapted for work in climates from 20 degrees below zero to 60 degrees above zero. The panel is usually installed on the roof, mainly in areas with good sunlight. It is available in various sizes. In particular, solar panels with a height and width of 2x1, 3x2 or 2x3 m, designed for houses, can uninterruptedly provide an apartment (a household) with solar electricity.

In order for the panel core to work in any conditions, it must be carefully, periodically wiped and cleaned of dust and dirt. The energy accumulated through the panel powers the battery in the controller. On the other hand, a battery, powered by sunlight during the day, generally provides houses with electricity at night.

Experts say that batteries that were used carelessly can last up to 10 years or even 15-30 years. When choosing batteries, you should pay special attention to the fact that they can accumulate energy according to the size of the solar panel.

Its usage system: in the event of a sudden power outage that you are using, the battery backup energy is automatically connected to the network and reaches certain hours?

Most solar cell manufacturers use mainly aluminum, photocells, and semiconductors. Based on this, a solar battery installed on the roof of a house emits 15-30 kilograms, depending on its power. Panels are made to order. Nowadays, some companies that sell solar cells offer finished products in various sizes. According to experts, solar panels of sizes 2x1, 3x2 and 2x3 m, intended for apartments, are in high demand on the market of Uzbekistan. It is better not to forget that installing such a panel on the roof of an apartment building involves certain difficulties. For example, when installing a panel on the roof of an apartment building, a cable is required to connect to the controller, then to the battery and inverter. The other cable must be grounded for safety.

During the production of solar panels and batteries, the climate of our country was taken into account. Therefore, they can be safely used even on rainy, snowy, cloudy days in autumn and winter.

Since the battery is powered by energy accumulated through solar panels, it is sufficient that sunlight reaches the panel for several hours. In the short term, a battery, powered by the sun, can provide a home with electricity even on cloudy days that last two to three days at a time.

Competitive types of energy can be obtained not only from the sun but also from the wind. The consistent development of the production of devices that generate wind

energy will also be important for providing the population with electricity in our country.

Battery power plants will be repaid in 5 years at today's prices. After 5 years, a person enjoys free electricity.

Where to install the panels and how many hours a day do they operate? Solar panels should be installed facing south. The roofs of the houses are the most appropriate solution. High-power solar panels are recommended to be installed in open areas, in unshaded places. When installed, hard parts may break when touched. If the panels break, repairs are not available.

Fig. 1. The elements of solar panels

1 - solar panels, 2 - controller, 3 - battery, 4 - inverter, 5 - consumer

In some areas of our country, especially in mountainous areas, the weather is cool and there are few sunny days. But the wind blows regularly. In such regions, wind equipment will prove useful. That is, apartments are supplied with electricity generated by solar panels on a sunny day in summer and by a generator during gusts of wind in winter. They produce from 1 to 10 kW per hour. This allows providing light to any large apartment and using household electrical appliances. The cost of the equipment will be 15-20 million soums rubles, considering the delivery and installation.

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